

MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION OF *ORMOCARPUM COCHINCHINENSE* (Lour.) Merr. USING CHLOROPLAST GENOME SIGNATURES

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MS Received: 15.02.2024; MS Revised: 20.03.2025; MS Accepted: 21.03.2025

MS 3365

(RESEARCH PAPER IN BOTANY)

Abstract

DNA barcoding is a powerful molecular technique widely used as a species identification tool in taxonomic studies. This present study highlights the usefulness of DNA barcoding for species identification of important medicinal plant *Ormocarpum cochinchinense*. The species are well recognized in the Indian traditional medicine system for curing bone fractures and associated disorders. The taxonomic identity of this species is often confused among the look-alike species. Therefore, the current study validates the efficacy of chloroplast DNA barcodes such as *rbcl*, and *trnH-psbA* for accurate species identification. Genomic DNA was isolated from two different accessions and successfully PCR amplified using universal primers. The *rbcl* and *trnH-psbA* DNA barcode markers recovered sequences of 584 bp and 357 bp, respectively. Primary validation of sequence using NCBI-BLAST algorithm showed 100% similarity with expected species in both the markers. The *trnH-psbA* DNA barcode displayed the highest variable sites, informative sites for parsimony, and nucleotide composition (AT and GC contents) compared to the *rbcl*. The phylogenetic tree constructed using the concatenated dataset of 18 DNA barcode sequences representing three *Ormocarpum* species revealed a unique genetic relationship with high bootstrap value. The present study is the first report on DNA barcoding of lesser-known species *O. cochinchinense* and provides valuable insights into genetic data useful for species authentication and conservation.

Keywords: DNA Barcodes; Phylogeny; *rbcl*; *trnH-psbA*; Genetic Divergence

Introduction

The medicinal plant *Ormocarpum cochinchinense* belongs to the Fabaceae is native to Southeast Asia. The species are highly valued in the traditional Indian system of medicine due to the long history of use in treating various ailments related to bone strength, osteoporosis, and other bone-associated disorders (Somashekar *et al.* 2023). The species are characterized by pinnate leaves with 10 to 3-foliolate with alternate leaflets, 3 to 5 yellow flowers in axillary racemes, and a pod with longitudinally striate, prickly, warted, and oblong seeds. Several studies highlighted that the use of this plant species in bone healing methods is specific to particular regions and tribal communities within India. However, in the southern state of Tamil Nadu, *O. cochinchinense* is widely preferred by the local vaidyas for bone treatments and is popularly referred to as “Elumbotti” as a vernacular name (Nagarajan and Pandian 2018). The accurate identification of *O. cochinchinense* from the look-alike species is crucial to get the expected health benefits during bone-related treatments. The existing taxonomic methods rely solely on morphological characters for species identification which encounters numerous challenges due to their complex variations and morphotypes (Yadav *et al.* 2024). Therefore, DNA sequence-based species identification is necessary for the identification of unique medicinal plants like *O. cochinchinense*.

DNA barcode signatures from the chloroplast genome offer a precise method for species identification using unique genetic barcodes for each species. Therefore, the DNA barcoding approach is widely used to distinguish between closely related species. The method relies on short and conserved DNA segments from the genome which are selected for their ability to delineate species (Hebert *et al.*, 2003). The major advantage of DNA barcoding is the use of less amount of samples for species identification and even small or degraded plant tissues could be identified at species level. Therefore, the current study utilized DNA barcoding as a potential tool for the identification of *O. cochinchinense* accession using *rbcl* and *trnH-psbA* DNA barcodes from the chloroplast genome. The phylogenetic tree and genetic divergence analysis were conducted for the first time in the study to understand the genetic composition and evolutionary relationships.

Material and Methods

The samples of *Ormocarpum cochinchinense* were collected from two locations such as Chennai and Tiruchirappalli Tamil Nadu, India. DNA was isolated with 100 mg of a sample using a modified CTAB protocol of Saghai Maroof *et al.* (1984). The concentration of DNA was checked on 0.8% agarose using Agarose gel electrophoresis (Bio-Rad, USA) and quantified using Nanodrop2000 (Thermo Scientific, USA). The genomic DNA of 50 ng was used as a template and amplified with *rbcl* and *trnH-psbA* DNA barcode (Levin *et al.* 2003; Kress *et al.*,

2005). The PCR reaction mixture contained 1X buffer with 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 200 μM dNTPs, 5 pmol of each primer, and 1 unit of Taq DNA polymerase with a final volume of 30 μL. The PCR was performed in a thermal cycler (Thermo Scientific, USA) and the PCR products were purified using a Silica Spin Column PCR Purification Kit (BioBasic, Canada). Purification of extension products was done using Sephadex G-50 followed by a run in ABI 3730 XL DNA Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, CA, USA). After DNA sequencing, each DNA barcode sequences were checked for quality using Sequence Scanner Software v.1.0 (Applied Biosystems, Calif., USA). The quality sequences were assembled and annotated using Codon Code Aligner version 4.2.4 (CodonCode Corporation, Mass., USA). Primary validation of DNA barcode sequences was done using the NCBI-BLAST homology search algorithm (<http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) with default parameters. Further, the sequences were analyzed for inter-specific genetic distances by assigning a query sequence to its closest match based on the genetic divergence in Taxon DNA v.1.6.2 (Meier *et al.* 2006). The concatenated dataset consisted of eighteen DNA sequences of *rbcl* and *trnH-psbA* markers representing four species of *Ormocarpum*. The phylogenetic tree was constructed using the maximum-likelihood method in MEGA v. 11 to resolve species complex among closely related species (Tamura *et al.* 2021). The phylogenetic analysis was done using the Jukes-cantor evolutionary model with bootstrap support of 10000 replications.

Results and Discussion

The prime obstacle in DNA barcoding is DNA extraction using laboratory protocols that may vary in different plant materials and groups (Lei *et al.* 2014). Similarly, the rate of PCR amplification could be affected due to the quality of the DNA extracted which is vital to access the efficacy of DNA barcodes (Poovitha *et al.* 2016). In this study, DNA was successfully isolated from the two accessions of *Ormocarpum cochinchinense* using fresh leaf samples using our standardized protocol. PCR amplification was successful using the universal primer of *rbcl* and *trnH-psbA* DNA barcode markers. Bidirectional DNA sequencing yielded 584 bp and 357 bp for *rbcl* and *trnH-psbA*, respectively. Primary validation of sequence using the NCBI-BLAST algorithm showed 100% similarity with expected species in the NCBI database. The average nucleotide composition of AT and GC contents of *trnH-psbA* was higher than the *rbcl* DNA barcode (Table 1). Similarly, the number of variable sites and parsimony informative sites of the *trnH-psbA* DNA barcode was significantly higher than the *rbcl* DNA barcode (Table 1.). The results were comparable to the previous studies that reported the highest number of variable sites, and parsimony informative sites in the *trnH-psbA* DNA barcode (Nithaniyal and Parani, 2016; Mishra *et al.* 2017).

Table 1. Details of nucleotide composition of the *Ormocarpum cochinchinense*

DNA barcode	Aligned length	Conserved site	Variable site	Parsimony informative site	AT (%)	GC (%)
<i>rbcL</i>	552	547	5	4	57.6	42.4
<i>trnH-psbA</i>	367	346	16	13	69.4	30.6

Genetic divergence analysis was carried out using 28 pairwise combinations of *rbcL* DNA barcode sequences belonging to three species *O. trichocarpum*, *O. kirkii*, and *O. cochinchinense*. The results showed a minimum intra-specific divergence of 0.0 % and a maximum inter-species divergence of 0.4%. In the case of the *trnH-psbA* DNA barcode, 15 pairwise combinations of the sequences belonging to two species *O. cochinchinense* and *O. kirkii* were analyzed. The results showed a minimum intra-specific divergence of 0.0 % and a maximum inter-species divergence of 4.0%. Genetic divergence analysis showed that the *trnH-psbA* marker could be able to differentiate closely related species. Previous research reported that the *rbcL* marker is highly conserved and improbable to show higher variation in closely related species (Newmaster *et al.* 2006; Dong *et al.* 2013).

The phylogenetic tree was constructed with the maximum likelihood method using *rbcL* and *trnH-psbA* DNA barcode sequences. A total of

eighteen DNA sequences of *rbcL* and *trnH-psbA* markers representing four species were used in this study. The species of *O. trichocarpum*, *O. kirkii*, and *O. cochinchinense* formed a separate clade in the *rbcL* marker (Fig. 1). Likewise, the accessions of *O. cochinchinense* and *O. kirkii* displayed a distinct clade using *trnH-psbA* marker (Fig. 2). Accessions of *Tephrosia purpurea* was used as an out-group. The results of the phylogenetic tree revealed that the *trnH-psbA* marker could be able to differentiate closely related species that the *rbcL* due to its higher genetic divergence. However, by considering the success of PCR amplification and DNA sequencing, *rbcL* could be used as a primary marker, and additional markers like *trnH-psbA* or ITS2 could be used for species-level identification. The present work provides the foundation for DNA barcoding of less studied species like *O. cochinchinense* to be useful in understanding the genetic relationship and conservation of species.

Fig. 1. Maximum-Likelihood (ML) tree of *rbcL* DNA barcode showing the genetic relationship of *Ormocarpum cochinchinense* and the numbers above branches indicates bootstrap values.

Fig. 2. Maximum-Likelihood (ML) tree of *trnH-psbA* DNA barcode showing the genetic relationship of *Ormocarpum cochinchinense* and the numbers above branches indicates bootstrap values.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this article.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful the Director, Botanical Survey of India and the Head of office, Western Regional centre, Botanical Survey of India, Pune, India

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